

**FORAMINIFERS AND PALYNOMORPHS IN THE SARMATIAN
DEPOSITS OF KARTLI (EASTERN GEORGIA):
STRATIGRAPHICAL AND PALAEOCLIMATOLOGICAL
IMPLICATIONS**

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Abstract

The foraminifers and palynomorphs from Sarmatian deposits of two sections, Nadarbazevi and Uplistsikhe, were studied. The foraminiferal assemblages allow establishing Late Volkhynian (beds with *Elphidium aculeatum*) and Early-Middle Bessarabian (beds with *Affinetrina voloshinovae* and *Porosonion aragviensis*) ages. The palynological analysis reflects the changes of ecological-systematical composition of the flora and allows interpreting the evolution of vegetation on the territory of Kartli depending on climatic fluctuations.

Key words: Eastern Georgia, Sarmatian, foraminifers, pollen and spores.

Introduction

Sarmatian deposits are widely distributed on the territory of Eastern Georgia (Fig.1). The mollusks of these deposits have been studied in detail [Buleishvili, 1960; Gruzinskaya, 1967], but investigation of the microfauna began only recently [Koiava, 2006].

Concerning pollen, there is only one work of P. Mchedlishvili and N. Mchedlishvili (1953), who studied the materials from a bore-hole in the central part of Kartli. The authors analyzed samples from Early, Middle and Late Sarmatian deposits and determined 28 forms. The Late Sarmatian palynological assemblages reflect the domination of the pollen of grasses.

First results of the micropalaeontological investigation of Sarmatian deposits of Eastern Georgia were published in 2008. In this work [Maissuradze et al., 2008], the lists of foraminifers and flora from the Nadarbazevi section are given and the changes in composition of micropalaeontological and palynological associations during the Middle Sarmatian are traced.

Fig.1. Geological map of the Gori area and location of the Nadarbazevi and Uplistsikhe sections (according to G. Gudjabidze, 2003)

Materials and Methods

In Figure 2, the stratigraphical schemes of the Sarmatian deposits in the Nadarbazevi and Uplistsikhe sections are given based on detailed sedimentological logging. The biostratigraphic zonation (N_1S_1 , N_1S_2) is based on [Koiava \(2006\)](#).

The list of foraminifers from the Nadarbazevi section is already published [Maissuradze et al., 2008]. Here only the list of microfauna from the Uplistsikhe section is given:

Elphidium macellum (Fichtel et Moll.), *E. aculeatum* (Orbigny), *E. rugosum* (Orbigny), *E. crispum* (Linne), *E. flexuosum* (Orbigny), *E. fichtelianum* (Orbigny), *E. hauerinum* (Orbigny), *E. reginum* (Orbigny), *E. grilli* Papp., *Porosonion subgranosum* (Egger), *P. granosum* (Orbigny), *P. martkobi* (Bogdanowicz), *P. subgranosum umboelatum* (Bogdanowicz), *Cycloforina complanata* (Gerke et Issaeva), *C. aff. predcarpatica* (Serova), *Sinuloculina consobrina sarmatica* (Gerke), *Varidentella reussi* (Bogdanowicz), *V. sarmatica* (Karrer), *Affinetrina guriana* (O. Djanelidze), *A. aff. ucrainica* (Serova), *Nonion bogdanowiczi* (Voloshinova), *N. aff. tumidulus* Pishvanova. In addition, *Ostracoda* are very common in this section.

In previous work [Maissuradze et al., 2008], the list of Sarmatian flora was published. It includes the results of palynological analysis of the Nadarbazevi section and of large plant remains from Sarmatian deposits of Kartli [Chelidze, 1979; 1987]. Later, new palynological material from Uplistsikhe as well as from the Nadarbazevi section was investigated that enriched our knowledge about the Sarmatian flora of Eastern Georgia. The full list of palynoflora from both sections is given below:

Sphagnum sp., *Lycopodium serratum* Tumb., *Lycopodium* sp., *Selaginella fusca* N. Mtchedl., *Selaginella* sp., *Bothrychium* sp., *Osmunda* sp., *Schizaea* sp., *Schizaeaceae* gen. indet., *Anemia* sp., *Mohria* sp., *Lygodium digitatum* Presl., *L. japonicum* Sw., *Lygodium* sp., *Cryptogramma* sp., *Pteridacidites boerzoenyensis* St. et Sh. (Nagy), *P. dentatiformis* Sh. et St., *P. grandifoliiformis* St. et Sh., *P. guriensis* Sh. et St., *P. longifoliiformis* Sh., et St., *P. remotifolioides* Sh. et St., *P. venustaeformis* St. et Sh., *P. verus* (N. Mtchedl.) Sh. et St., *Pteridacidites* sp., *Marsilea* sp., *Anogramma* sp., *Onychium* sp., *Pityrogramma* sp., *Clavifera* sp., *Gleichenia* sp., *Gleicheniaceae* gen. indet., *Polypodium aureum* L., *P. pliogenicum* Ram., *P. verrucatum* Ram., *Polypodium* sp., *Verrucatosporite histiopteroides* W. Kr., *Pyrossia* sp., *Polypodiaceae* gen. indet.,

Fig.2. The stratigraphical schemes of the Nadarbazevi and Uplistsikhe sections.

Hymenophyllum sp., *Cibotium* sp. *Dicksonia reticulata* Purc., *Dicksonia spanditocincta* Purc., *Dicksonia unitotuberata* Purc., *Dicksonia* sp., *Alsophylla* sp., *Cyathea* sp., *Hemitelia* sp., *Asplenium* sp., *Cistopteris* sp., *Microlepia* sp., *Dryopteris* sp., *Thelypteris* sp., *Polystichum* sp., *Ginkgo* sp., *Dacrydium* sp., *Podocarpus* sp., *Phyllocladus* sp., *Araucaria* sp., *Abies ciliticaeformis* N.Mtchedl., *A.nordmanniana* (Stev.) Spach., *Abies* sp., *Cathaya* sp., *Cedrus saueriae* N.Mtchedl., *Cedrus* sp., *Keteleeria caucasica* Ram., *Picea minor* N.Mtchedl., *Picea* sp., *Pinus* sp., *Pseudolarix* sp., *Pseudotsuga* sp., *Tsuga aff.canadensis* (L.) Carr., *T.aff.pattoniana* Engelm., *Tsuga* sp., *Sciadopitys* sp., *Cryptomeria* sp., *Cunninghamia* sp., *Metasequoia* sp., *Sequoia* sp., *Taxodium* sp., *Taxodiaceae* gen.indet., *Libocedrus* sp., *Juniperus* sp., *Cupressaceae* gen.indet., *Ephedra* sp., *Comptonia* sp., *Myrica aff.notabilis* Gladk., *Myrica* sp., *Carya aquatica* (Michx.) Nutt., *C.aff.cordiformis* (Wandh.) C.Koch, *Carya* sp., *Engelhardia* sp., *Platycarya* sp., *Pterocarya* sp., *Juglans cinerea* L., *J.regia* L., *Juglans* sp., *Juglandaceae* gen.indet., *Salix* sp., *Alnus* sp., *Betula* sp., *Carpinus betulus* L., *Carpinus caucasica* Grossh., *Carpinus* sp., *Corylus* sp., *Castanea* sp., *Castanopsis* sp., *Fagus* sp., *Lithocarpus* sp., *Quercus* sp., *Celtis* sp., *Ulmus foliacea* Gilib., *Ulmus* sp., *Zelkova aff.serrata* (Thunb.) Macino, *Zelkova carpiunifolia* (Pall.) Dipp., *Eucommia ulmoides* Oliv., *Ficus* sp., *Polygonum* sp., *Caryophyllaceae* gen.indet., *Chenopodiaceae* gen.indet., *Liriodendron* sp., *Magnolia grandiflora* L., *Magnolia megafigurata* (W.Kr.) Ram., *Magnolia* sp., *Annona* sp., *Cinnamomum* sp., *Laurus* sp., *Lauraceae* gen.indet., *Ranunculus* sp., *Menispermum* sp., *Platanus* sp., *Liquidambar styraciflua* L., *Liquidambar* sp., *Corylopsis* sp., *Disanthus* sp., *Distyliopsis* sp., *Fothergilla* sp., *Hamamelis* sp., *Parrotia* sp., *Sycopsis colchica* Ram., *Hamamelidaceae* gen.indet., *Cercidiphyllum* sp., *Sorbus* sp., *Rosaceae* gen.indet., *Fabaceae* gen.inet., *Geranium* sp., *Rhus* sp., *Acer* sp., *Aesculus* sp., *Ilex* sp., *Euonymus* sp., *Staphylea* sp., *Parthenocissus* sp., *Vitis* sp., *Tilia* sp., *Sterculia* sp., *Viola* sp., *Myrtaceae* gen.indet., *Alangium* sp., *Nyssa* sp., *Cornaceae* gen.indet., *Aralia* sp., *Dendropanax* sp., *Araliaceae* gen.indet., *Apiaceae* gen.indet., *Rhododendron* sp., *Sapotaceae* gen.indet., *Symplocos* sp., *Fraxinus* sp., *Oleaceae* gen.indet., *Lonicera* sp., *Lamiaceae* gen.indet., *Plantago* sp., *Boraginaceae* gen.indet., *Artemisia* sp., *Cirsium* sp., *Asteraceae* gen.indet., *Poaceae* gen.indet., *Nipa* sp., *Arecaceae* gen.indet., *Sparganium* sp., *Typha* sp., *Tricolpopollenites edmundi* (R.Pot.) Th. et Pf., *Tricolporopollenites wackersdorfensis* Thiele-Pfeiffer.

Results and Discussion

The foraminifers in the Nadarbazevi and Uplistsikhe sections are characterized by identical complexes. However, the Nadarbazevi section is richer in number of species and specimens (Figs. 3, 4).

According to the foraminifers, the lower beds (samples 1-4) in the Uplistsikhe section are dated as Early Sarmatian (N₁S₁; Koiava, 2006), which corresponds to the Volkhynian substage. Only the Late Volkhynian layers with *Elphidium aculeatum* are exposed here [Koiava, 2006]. The sediments are represented by sandy-argillaceous facies with intercalated beds of sandstone, conglomerate, and limestone. They are characterized by more or less monotonous assemblages of foraminifers, in which typically *Porosonion subgranosum* (sample 1) or *Elphidium macellum* (sample 2) are dominant. Together with these predominant species also *Porosonion martkobi*, *P.granosum*, *Elphidium aculeatum*, *E. hauerinum*, *E. flexuosum*, *E. grilli*, *Nonion bogdanowiczi* are present. *Varidentella reussi*, *Cycloforina complanata*, and small specimens of *Ostracoda* are rare.

The deposits of the upper part of the Uplistsikhe section (samples 5-12) are characterized by foraminifer assemblages indicating a Middle Sarmatian age (N₁S₂). The sediments correspond to the Early Bessarabian substage or to layers with *Affinetrina voloshinovae*, which are widely distributed in the Sarmatian of Eastern Georgia [Koiava, 2006]. In Uplistsikhe, this interval is represented by shallow water facies (marls including sandstone and limestone beds) and

characterized by numerous many-chambered (10-14) specimens of *A. voloshinovae*, not typical for this species. Such are *Porosonion subgranosum* and *P. subgranosum umboelatum*, or big thick-walled many-chambered representatives of the genus *Elphidium* (*E. macellum*, *crispum*, *fichtelianum*, *flexuosum*). More rarely (samples 3, 10), single species of *Affinetrina*, *Cycloforina*, *Varidentella* are present, which display large, coarse, and thick tests. Such morphological features are characteristic also for *Ostracoda*, which are enriched in this complex.

Fig.3. Relative abundance of foraminifer genera in the Uplistsikhe section (for sample position see Fig. 2).

Consequently, in the Uplistsikhe section, the Late Volkhynian (beds with *Elphidium aculeatum*) and the Early Bessarabian (beds with *Affinetrina voloshinovae*) are well established.

The first results of micropalaeontological investigations of the Nadarbazevi section have already been published [(Maissuradze et al., 2008)]. The study of additional material now allows establishing new stratigraphical levels with characteristic assemblages of foraminifers (Fig. 4.). The section is composed of Early Sarmatian (N₁S₁, Late Volkhynian) and Middle Sarmatian (N₁S₂, Early-Middle Bessarabian) deposits. The Late Volkhynian assemblage (samples -3; -1”) is characterized by very small, typically small-chambered (6-8) *Porosonion subgranosum* and *P. martkobi* (10-15 specimens) and single (not more than 3-4 specimens) *Elphidium hauerinum*, *E. macellum*, *Nonion bogdanowiczi*, and *Varidentella reussi*. Numerous otoliths of fishes, fragments and embryos of mollusks and - seldom - small ostracodes are also present.

The lower part of the Middle Sarmatian (Early Bessarabian) is defined by beds containing *Affinetrina voloshinovae* (samples 0-8). This part is characterized by a rich and diverse assemblage of foraminifers, in which bigger than usual *Porosonion* and *Elphidium* are dominant, similar to synchronous forms from the Uplistsikhe section. Only the assemblage of sample 3 is different. This is a typical miliolidian complex, which is characteristic for argillaceous deposits: *Varidentella*

reussi, *V. sarmatica*, *V. latelaculata*, *Cycloforina complanata*, *C. aff. predcarpatica*, *C. aff. hauerina*, *Sinuloculina consobrina sarmatica*, *S. angustioris*, *Affinetrina* sp., *Spiroloculina kolesnikovi*, *Articulina sarmatica*, *A. problema*, and numerous *Ostracoda*.

Fig. 4. Relative abundance of foraminifer genera in the Nadarbazevi section (for sample position see Fig. 2).

The deposits of the upper part of the Nadarbazevi section (samples 7-1k) have already been described in detail [Maissuradze et al., 2008]. Additional material allows only specifying their age as Middle Bessarabian (beds with *Porosonion aragviensis*) [Koiava, 2006].

In the deposits of the Nadarbazevi and Uplistsikhe sections, pollen and spores were seen mainly in the Middle Sarmatian and in the upper part of the Early Sarmatian. However, not in all samples the number of grains was large enough for calculating the percentages.

The diagrams in Figs. 5 and 6 reflect the ecological-systemasical composition of the flora. In the beginning of these diagrams the composition of palyno-assemblages is given: pollen of woody plants, herbaceous plants, and cryptogams. The assemblages are dominated by woody plants, followed by spores of ferns. Grasses are presented by a small number of grains, except in the upper beds of the Nadarbazevi section.

The woody plants are divided into two groups: conifers and angiosperms. In turn, the conifers are also divided into two groups: the forms of temperate climate (*Abies*, *Picea*, *Tsuga*), with only minor participation in the composition of the palynocomplex; and the forms of warm-temperate and subtropical climate (*Podocarpus*, *Dacrydium*, some *Cedrus*, *Cathaya*, *Phyllocladus*,

etc.). By percentage these forms predominate over conifers of temperate climate. The curve of pine is given separately, as a form with wide ecological range. Among angiosperm woody plants, we distinguish two groups: the plants of warm-temperate climate (*Fagaceae*, *Ulmaceae*, *Betulaceae*, *Juglandaceae*) and forms of subtropical climate (*Myricaceae*, *Hamamelidaceae*, *Magnoliaceae*, *Alangium*, *Sapotaceae*, etc.).

The distribution of spores is given separately in the diagram. They are presented mainly by subtropical forms: *Schizaeaceae*, *Anemiaceae*, *Lygodiaceae*, *Pteridaceae*, *Gleicheniaceae*, *Polypodiaceae*, *Dicksoniaceae*, etc.

Finally, the distribution of pollen of subxerophilous forms (*Chenopodiaceae*, *Asteraceae*, *Ephedra*) is given.

The second type of diagram (Fig. 7) is built on the basis of the landscape-phytocenological method. The aim of this diagram is to show the character of vegetation cover and its evolution through time, and to distinguish the stages of development of vegetation and climate.

The assemblages were divided into three groups: temperate-dark-conifer forest of the upper mountain belt, and subtropical-warm-temperate polydominant forests of the lower and middle mountain belts. We also include subtropical conifers and ferns, which formed the lower layer of the forests. The curve of pine – intrazonal plants as indicators of humidity is given separately in the diagram.

The analysis of the palynological distribution through time (Figs. 5, 6, 7) allows distinguishing 9 stages in the development of vegetation and climate in Kartli during the Early and Middle Sarmatian.

Stage I (upper part of the Early Sarmatian, Uplistsikhe section, sample 4) is characterized by a small area of dark conifers and the domination of pine forests over the polydominant forests. The climate was subtropical with low humidity.

Stage II was established in the Uplistsikhe section (sample 5). The area of polydominant forests became smaller. The area of pine increased. The territory of dark conifers was the same as in stage I. Stages I and II differed by the regime of humidity, which in stage II was lower.

Stage III is distinguished by the material from the Uplistsikhe section (sample 7) and the Nadarbazevi section (sample 0). The characteristic feature of this stage is the high percentage of plants of polydominant forests and the low proportion of pine and dark conifers. The climate was subtropical with high humidity and probably corresponded to the climatic optimum of the Middle Sarmatian. According to the foraminifers, the upper boundary of this stage is likely the boundary between lower and middle parts of Middle Sarmatian (See Fig. 2).

Stage IV is also established in both sections (sample 9 in Uplistsikhe and sample 3 in Nadarbazevi). The characteristic feature of this stage is the increase in number of plants of temperate climate, the reduction of the area of polydominant forests, and some increase of pine. In comparison with the previous stage, of temperature and humidity were decreasing.

Stage V is distinguished by the palynological data of the Uplistsikhe section (samples 10, 11, 12). To this stage we attribute also the samples 4 and 8k of the Nadarbazevi section. The assemblages of both sections reflect a similar picture of development of vegetation: the predominance of polydominant forests and reduction of area of darkconifer and pine forests. Probably it also was the climatic optimum, with subtropical and humid climate.

About the other stages of development of vegetation and climate of Kartli during the Middle Sarmatian we can judge only by material from the Nadarbazevi section.

Stage VI (samples 7k, 6k) reflects the increase of area of dark conifers and pine, and reduction of area of polydominant forests. The climate was warm-temperate with somewhat reduced humidity.

Stage VII (samples 5k, 4k) is characterized by reduction of the role of pine and by an increase of the area of polydominant forests. The climate was close to subtropical with high humidity.

During stage VIII (sample 3k), the area of polydominant forest was reduced and the territory of pine increased. The dark conifers continued to occupy stable areas during the stages VI, VII, and VIII. The climate was warm-temperate with low humidity.

Stage IX (samples 2k, 5, 6) is distinguished by reduction of area of dark conifers and pine. The area of polydominant forests increased but their composition changed. The number of subtropical ferns reduced. Predominant components were warm-temperate plants colonizing flood-plain forests. Judging from the diagram of the Nadarbazevi section (Fig. 5), characteristic features of this stage were reduction of forests at whole and increase of open spaces.

Fig. 5. Pollen diagram of Sarmatian deposits of the Nadarbazevi section (for sample position see Fig. 2). Temperate conifers: *Abies*, *Picea*, *Tsuga*, some species of *Cedrus*; warm-temperate and subtropical conifers: *Dacrydium*, *Podocarpus*, *Phyllocladus*, *Cathaya*, some species of *Cedrus*, *Ginkgo*, etc.; warm-temperate leaf-bearing forms: *Fagaceae*, *Ulmaceae*, *Betulaceae*, *Juglandaceae*; subtropical leaf-bearing forms: *Myricaceae*, *Magnoliaceae*, *Hamamelidaceae*, *Araliaceae*, *Arecaceae*, etc.; subtropical and tropical ferns: *Pteridaceae*, *Polypodiaceae*, *Gleicheniaceae*, *Schizaeaceae*, etc.; subxerophilous forms: *Ephedra*, *Chenopodiaceae*, *Asteraceae*, etc.

Fig.6. Pollen diagram of Sarmatian deposits of the Uplistsikhe section (for sample position see Fig. 2). Temperate conifers: *Abies*, *Picea*, *Tsuga*, some species of *Cedrus*; warm-temperate and subtropical conifers: *Dacrydium*, *Podocarpus*, *Phyllocladus*, *Cathaya*, some species of *Cedrus*, *Ginkgo*, etc.; warm-temperate leaf-bearing forms: *Fagaceae*, *Ulmaceae*, *Betulaceae*, *Juglandaceae*; subtropical leaf-bearing forms: *Myricaceae*, *Magnoliaceae*, *Hamamelidaceae*, *Araliaceae*, *Arecaceae*, etc.; subtropical and tropical ferns: *Pteridaceae*, *Polypodiaceae*, *Gleicheniaceae*, *Schizaeaceae*, etc.; subxerophilous forms: *Ephedra*, *Chenopodiaceae*, *Asteraceae*, etc.

Conclusions

The Sarmatian deposits of Kartli (Eastern Georgia) in the Nadarbazevi and Uplistsikhe sections were analyzed by microfaunistical and palynological methods.

In these sections, Late Volkhinian, Early Bessarabian and Middle Bessarabian deposits are present. They are characterized by homotypic complexes of foraminifers, in which shallow water, euryhaline forms are dominated. The similarity of the assemblages, their ecological characteristics, the morphological peculiarity of the dominant forms (sizes, sculpture of the tests), and the

composition of accompanying microorganisms (otoliths, mollusks, bryozoans, algae, ostracodes) testify that in this region, during Early-Middle Sarmatian, the sea was brackish (absence of stenohaline forms). The water was shallow, warm, saturated by oxygen (big sizes of tests) and by calcium carbonate (thickness, ornamentation or sculpture of walls of tests).

Fig.7. The main stages of climate and vegetation development in the territory of Kartli (Eastern Georgia) during the Middle Sarmatian according to palynological analysis of deposits of the Nadarabazevi and Uplistsikhe sections.

The Late Volkhinian and Early Bessarabian deposits in the Nadarbazevi and Uplistsicke sections are well correlated due to the similarity of foraminifer assemblages.

The palynological analysis of these two sections allows distinguishing 9 stages in the history of development of vegetation and climate in Kartli.

In stages I and II, the temperatures were rather high, close to those of subtropical zones but the humidity was low, especially in stage II, when subtropical polydominant forests occupied a comparably small area. In stage III, the humidity was higher and the subtropical forests increased their area, which then was the largest of the whole Middle Sarmatian. Therefore, stage III can be considered as climatic optimum. Nearly the same situation occurred in stage V, which also can be considered as climatic optimum. These two optima were separated by an interval with lower temperatures (stage IV). In this time, temperate dark-conifer forests increased their area. In stage V, their territory decreased again. In the following stages (VI, VII, VIII), they preserved nearly equal areas till the middle part of the Middle Sarmatian (stage IX). During the whole time of deposition of the Nadarbazevi and Uplistsicke sections, the area of darkconifers never intersected with the area of pine and polydominant forests. The evolution of vegetation of Eastern Georgia during the Middle Sarmatian is expressed mainly in periodical domination of either polydominant forests or pine forests. This was accentuated in the middle part of the Middle Sarmatian (stages VI, VII, VIII). Towards the end of the middle part of the Middle Sarmatian (stage IX), the forests began to decline as a whole as did the number of subtropical ferns, and the role of plants characteristic for vegetation of open spaces increased. Warm-temperate and subtropical plants composing riparian forests continued to exist.

We can conclude that the main climatic factor, which influenced the development of vegetation of Eastern Georgia was the regime of humidity. This is in accordance with the paleogeographical changes that took place at the end of the Middle Sarmatian, one of the turning points in the Neogene history of the Caucasus [Tsagareli, Astakhov, 1971]. As a result of orogenic movements, the surface area of the sea decreased, and on the territory of Eastern Georgia dry land with continental climate originated. In the Late Sarmatian and following time, according to palaeontological data [Mchedlishvili P.A., Mchedlishvili N.D. 1953; Meladze, 1967], steppes and semi-deserts dominated on the territory of Kartli.

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